

1 Morphological and genetic diversity of maize landraces along an altitudinal
2 gradient in the Southern Andes

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24

25 **Abstract**

26

27 Maize (*Zea mays* ssp. *mays*) is a major cereal crop worldwide and is traditionally or
28 commercially cultivated almost all over the Americas. The northwestern region of
29 Argentina (NWA) constitutes one of the main diversity hotspots of the Southern Andes,
30 with contrasting landscapes and a large number of landraces. Despite the extensive
31 collections performed by the “Banco Activo de Germoplasma INTA Pergamino,
32 Argentina” (BAP), most of them have not been characterized yet. Here we report the
33 morphological and molecular evaluation of 30 accessions collected from NWA, along an
34 altitudinal gradient between 1120 and 2950 meters above sea level (masl). Assessment of
35 morphological variation in a common garden allowed the discrimination of two groups,
36 which differed mainly in endosperm type and overall plant size. Although the groups
37 retrieved by the molecular analyses were not consistent with morphological clusters, they
38 showed a clear pattern of altitudinal structuring. Affinities among accessions were not in
39 accordance with racial assignments. Overall, our results revealed that there are two maize
40 gene pools co-existing in NWA, probably resulting from various waves of maize
41 introduction in pre-Columbian times as well as from the adoption of modern varieties by
42 local farmers.

43 In conclusion, the NWA maize landraces preserved at the BAP possess high morphological
44 and molecular variability. Our results highlight their potential as a source of diversity for
45 increasing the genetic basis of breeding programs and provide useful information to guide
46 future sampling and conservation efforts.

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50 **Introduction**

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52 Genetic erosion is the main problem associated with the selection and improvement of
53 agronomically important species. Despite the progress achieved in terms of productivity,
54 modern breeding takes advantage of only a small fraction of the available variability,
55 restricting the response of crops to pests, diseases and environmental changes [1–3]. The
56 use of landraces or related wild species provides the opportunity to counteract this process,
57 widening the narrow genetic base of elite germplasm.

58 The recent revalorization of landraces as sources of diversity and beneficial alleles has been
59 expressed through different initiatives aimed at providing an extensive characterization of
60 germplasm bank collections. This characterization involves molecular and phenotypic
61 aspects of maize and other crops [e.g., <https://seedsofdiscovery.org/>; www.amaizing.fr; 4].

62 The high genetic diversity of maize landraces in the Americas has been thoroughly
63 documented. [e.g. 5–11]. So far, however, most studies have adopted a macro-regional
64 approach, where large geographic areas are represented by a small number of accessions
65 and each accession is represented by a small number of individuals or sample pools. The
66 information provided by this type of strategy is extremely valuable in characterizing
67 variability, but it is insufficient for other genetic population analyses, especially those
68 linked to environmental variables and local adaptations. Moreover, the limited number of
69 studies aiming to examine the relationship among phenotype, genotype and environment
70 through the combination of molecular and morphological data may be accounted for by the
71 difficulty in seed germination and growth of landraces outside their native range.

72 The northwestern region of Argentina (NWA) is the southernmost distribution limit of the
73 Andean maize landraces. This region is characterized by a remarkable topographic
74 variability, as it comprises six phytogeographic provinces located within a relatively limited
75 area (i.e, Yungas, Chaco, Puna, Pre-Puna, Monte and High Andean) [12]. Two contrasting
76 examples of its great environmental diversity are the subtropical forests of the Yungas
77 (distributed between 400 and 3000 masl and with annual mean precipitation increasing
78 between 600 and 3000 mm with altitude), and the ridges and valleys of the Sub-Andean

79 mountains (precipitation below 200 mm/ year, mainly concentrated in the summer
80 months)[12].

81 More than 50% of the *ca.* 56 maize landraces described for northern Argentina are native to
82 NWA, making it one of the main diversity hotspots of the Southern Andes [13,14]. In
83 accordance, the most ancient records of maize from the American Southern Cone
84 correspond to NWA and date to 3500 years BP [15]. Currently, the native germplasm is
85 traditionally cultivated between 400 and 3600 masl, thus being exposed to a wide range of
86 thermal amplitudes and rainfall regimes [13]. So far, only a limited number of maize
87 landraces from NWA have been characterized either molecularly and/or cytogenetically
88 [16,17]. Although most of these races are associated with the Andean Complex, as defined
89 by Mc. Clintock et al. [18], the presence of germplasm from other origins (e.g. popcorn and
90 tropical maize) was also detected [16,17].

91 The present scenario of increasing food demand and climate change highlights the need for
92 materials capable of growing under extreme conditions, such as the NWA landraces.
93 Therefore, the characterization of the accessions in germplasm banks is important in
94 tackling these challenges. Today, the “Banco Activo de Germoplasma de maíz in EEA-
95 INTA Pergamino, Argentina” (BAP), preserves more than 2500 accessions from over 10
96 collections performed between 1977 and 1994. As in the rest of the world, most of them are
97 scarcely used due to the poor knowledge of their characteristics and genetic merit, as well
98 as to the almost complete absence of molecular descriptions (Eyhérabide *et al.*, 2005;
99 López *et al.*, 2005). In this study, we present the morphological and molecular
100 characterization of 30 accessions (17 landraces) of BAP from NWA, collected at sites
101 between 1120 and 2950 masl. They were sown in a common garden at 2300 masl and
102 characterized for 19 morphological characters and 22 SSR loci to evaluate their agronomic
103 potential, determine their genetic constitution and guide *in situ* and *ex situ* conservation
104 efforts.

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111 **Materials and Methods**

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113 **Plant material**

114 We selected a set of 30 accessions corresponding to 17 different maize landraces, which
115 covered a broad altitudinal range (collection sites between 1120 and 2950 masl) and
116 represented the morphological diversity occurring in NWA (Fig 1, S1Table).

117

118 **Fig 1. Collection sites of the landraces included in this study.** Further details are
119 provided in S1 Table.

120

121 **Morphological characterization**

122 All the accessions were morphologically characterized at the Instituto de Pequeña
123 Agricultura Familiar (IPAF), Hornillos, Jujuy Province, Argentina (23°65'17" S,
124 65°43'55"W; 2300 masl). One-hundred seeds per accession were sown under a randomized
125 block design with two replicates. The elementary plots consisted of two rows of 5 m length,
126 spaced 0.5 m apart. A conventional tillage was applied, with manual weeding and
127 supplementary irrigation. No fertilizer or insecticide was added.

128 Nineteen agro-morphological descriptors, selected from the list of descriptors of the
129 International Board for Plant Genetic Resources (CIMMYT/IBPGR, Roma, 1991,
130 [https://www.bioversityinternational.org/e-library/publications/detail/descriptors-for-](https://www.bioversityinternational.org/e-library/publications/detail/descriptors-for-maizedescriptores-para-maizdescripteurs-pour-le-mais/)

131 [maizedescriptores-para-maizdescripteurs-pour-le-mais/](https://www.bioversityinternational.org/e-library/publications/detail/descriptors-for-maizedescriptores-para-maizdescripteurs-pour-le-mais/)), were scored. The following
132 vegetative traits were assessed: plant height (PH), number of leaves (NL), number of leaves
133 above the uppermost ear (NLA), uppermost leaf length (ULL), uppermost leaf width
134 (ULW), venation index (VI) and tillering index (TI). The descriptors measured on the tassel
135 were tassel length (TL), tassel peduncle length (TPL), tassel branching space (TBS),
136 number of primary branches on tassel (NPBT), number of secondary branches on tassel
137 (NSBT) and number of tertiary branches on tassel (NTBT). The variables recorded on the
138 ear were uppermost ear height (EH), ear peduncle length (EPL), ear diameter (ED), mean
139 number of ears per accession (MNE), number of rows of kernels per ear (NRK), and
140 number of kernels per row (NKR).

141 Vegetative and tassel descriptors were measured on seven to 10 plants per accession per
142 block. The ear and kernel descriptors were measured on 10 ears per accession, which were
143 harvested from the same plants used to evaluate vegetative and tassel descriptors.

144

145 **Morphological data analysis**

146 Summary statistics, coefficients of variation (CV) and correlations between traits were
147 computed using InfoStat 2018 [19].

148 Using the accessions as OTUs, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed
149 based on average trait values. To avoid biases related to the difference in scale between the
150 variables, data were standardized so that their average was zero and the standard deviation
151 was equal to one. R packages *FactoMineR* [20] and *factoextra* [21] were used to compute
152 and visualize PCA results. Groups of accessions were identified by the K-means algorithm
153 [22], employing the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) [23] to find the most likely
154 number of clusters. These analyses were conducted with the R package *adeget* [24].

155

156 **Microsatellite typing**

157 Genomic DNA was extracted from lyophilized young leaves (2–3 days old), germinated
158 from individual kernels following Dellaporta *et al.* [25]. The quality and concentration of
159 the genomic DNA were assessed using NanodropND1000 3.3 software (NanoDrop
160 Technologies®).

161 Twenty-two SSR loci were selected from a preliminary survey of 27, and only loci with
162 unambiguous interpretation were used for this analysis (S2 Table). Genotyping of the SSRs
163 was performed using PCR with fluorescent labeled primers (HEX and FAM). PCR
164 products were size-separated on an Applied Biosystems automated sequencer (ABI 3130
165 XL) and allele calling was carried out with GeneMapper® 4.0 software (Applied
166 Biosystems, Foster City, USA) using a commercial size standard for allele size assignment
167 (GeneScan ROX 500, Applied Biosystems®). Automatic allele calls were subsequently
168 confirmed reviewing all electropherograms.

169

170 **Microsatellite data analysis**

171 Mean number of alleles per locus (A), allele frequency, observed (H_o) and expected (H_e)
172 heterozygosities, allelic richness (R_s) [26], presence of population-specific alleles (hereafter
173 referred to as private alleles) and Wright's fixation indices were assessed using Fstat 2.9.3.2
174 software [27]. Genetic distances among accessions were computed according to Nei [28]
175 using GeneAIEx 6 (Peakall & Smouse, 2006).
176 Genetic structure was examined using the Bayesian model-based approach of Pritchard et
177 al. [29] implemented in STRUCTURE 2.3.4 software
178 (<http://www.pritch.bsd.uchicago.edu>). The number of clusters evaluated ranged from 1 to
179 10. The analysis was performed using 10 replicates runs per K value, a burn-in period
180 length of 500,000 and a run length of 1,000,000. No prior information on the origin of
181 individuals was used to define the clusters and the correlated frequency model was used for
182 all the analyses. The model assumes that the frequencies in the different populations are
183 likely to be similar due to common ancestry [30]. The deltaK method of Evanno et al [31]
184 was used to identify the most likely number of clusters, using the web tool STRUCTURE
185 HARVESTER [32]. Accessions were assigned to a given cluster when average membership
186 coefficients were higher than an arbitrary cut-off value of 85%. Graphical display of
187 STRUCTURE outputs was performed via the distruct program version 1.1 [33].
188 Correlations between genetic, morphological, and altitudinal distances were evaluated
189 using Mantel tests (Mantel, 1964). Analyses were conducted based on Spearman
190 correlation coefficients using the *mantel* function of the R package *vegan* [34]. We also
191 inspected Spearman correlations between altitude, morphological traits and genetic
192 diversity measures using InfoStat version 2018 [19]. Significance was assessed with
193 permutation tests (1000 permutations). All graphics were obtained with the R package
194 *ggplot2* [35].

195

196 **Results**

197

198 **Morphological variation**

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200 Global averages for the 19 quantitative agro-morphological traits scored in the study are
201 presented in Table 1, along with standard deviations and coefficients of variation. Data for
202 individual accessions are provided in S3 Table.

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Table 1. Quantitative trait variation in 30 maize accessions from Northwestern Argentina (NWA).

<i>Trait</i>	Mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
PH (cm)	164.16	22.94	14
NL	12.38	1.63	13
NLA	5.99	0.53	9
ULL (cm)	65.68	7.69	12
ULW (cm)	9.26	0.78	8
VI	2.50	0.35	14
TI	0.86	0.63	73
TL (cm)	35.41	7.51	21
TPL (cm)	17.48	5.21	30
TBS (cm)	13.15	3.31	25
NPBT	16.38	3.10	19
NSBT	6.64	3.05	46
NTBT	0.23	0.38	16.5
EH (cm)	81.55	18.93	23
EPL (cm)	8.30	2.13	26
ED (cm)	4.01	0.31	8
MNE	2.55	0.43	17
NRK	12.26	2.08	17
NKR	30.53	4.13	13

PH: plant height, **NL:** number of leaves, **NLA:** number of leaves above the uppermost ear, **ULL:** uppermost leaf length, **ULW:** uppermost leaf width, **VI:** venation index, **TI:** tillering index, **TL:** tassel length, **TPL:** tassel peduncle length, **TBS:** tassel branching space, **NPBT:** number of primary branches on tassel, **NSBT:** number of secondary branches on tassel, **NTBT:** number of tertiary branches on tassel, **EH:** uppermost ear height, **EPL:** ear peduncle length, **ED:** ear diameter, **MNE:** mean number of ears, **NRK:** number of rows of kernels per ear, **NKR:** number of kernels per row

207

208 All the morphological characters analyzed showed considerable levels of variation across
209 accessions (Table 1). The highest coefficients of variation were observed in TI (73%),
210 NSBT (46%) and TPL (30%), while the most homogeneous traits were NLA, ULW and
211 ED, with coefficients of variation of 9, 8 and 8%, respectively.
212 The analysis of association between variables revealed 56 significant correlations, which
213 decreased to 20 after Bonferroni correction (S4 Table). Most of the significant correlations
214 were moderate, except for PH-EH ($r=0.87$) and TBS- NSBT ($r=0.76$).

215 Analysis of morphological variation using the K-means algorithm allowed the identification
216 of two main groups (K=2, BIC=86.43, diffNgroup criterion) (S3 Table). Accession
217 assignment and distribution along the first two dimensions of the PCA are shown in Fig 2a.
218 The first PC accounted for 32.6% of the variance and was negatively associated with the
219 variables that made the largest contributions to this component, i.e. PH, EH, TBS, and NLA
220 (Fig 2b). The second PC accounted for 13.9% of total variance. It was positively associated
221 with NTBT and negatively correlated with TI, MNE, and ULL.

222

223 **Fig 2. (a) Principal Component Analysis based on 19 agro-morphological traits.**

224 Accessions are color-coded according to the groups identified by the K-means procedure.

225 **(b) Correlations and variable contributions to the first two PCs.** The scale corresponds

226 to variable contributions. PH: plant height, NL: number of leaves, NLA: number of leaves

227 above the uppermost ear, ULL: uppermost leaf length, ULW: uppermost leaf width, VI:

228 venation index, TI: tillering index, TL: tassel length, TPL: tassel peduncle length, TBS:

229 tassel branching space, NPBT: number of primary branches on tassel, NSBT: number of

230 secondary branches on tassel, NTBT: number of tertiary branches on tassel, EH: uppermost

231 ear height, EPL: ear peduncle length, ED: ear diameter, MNE: mean number of ears, NRK:

232 number of rows of kernels per ear, NKR: number of kernels per row.

233

234 The first group, G1 (black), presented a heterogeneous grain conformation, with accessions

235 showing dent, semi-dent, sweet, flint and floury endosperm types (S1 Table). In this

236 cluster, plants were taller and leafier than those in the second group, G2 (blue). In addition,

237 tassel peduncles were shorter, the tillering index was lower, ear diameter was larger and the

238 average number of grains per ear was 372 (S3 Table).

239 On the other hand, the G2 group comprised low-height accessions with pop, flint or semi-

240 flint endosperm, fewer leaves, longer tassel peduncles, shorter branching space and very

241 few tassel secondary branches. These accessions produced only a few ears per plant. The

242 ears had smaller mean diameter and fewer grains per row than those in group G1, but a

243 larger number of rows of kernels, resulting in a mean number of grains per ear of 350 (S3

244 Table).

245 The third PC (12.1% of total variance) maintained the same groupings, but further divided
 246 G1 into two sub-clusters, separating accessions with higher TPL and lower VI from the rest
 247 (S1 Fig 1, S5 Table).

248

249 **Molecular diversity**

250 Genotyping of 22 SSR loci in 379 individuals revealed a total of 419 alleles (S6 Table).
 251 Diversity estimates per locus and accession are provided in S7 Table. The overall number
 252 of alleles per locus varied from eight (ϕ 072) to 42 (bnlg244), with a mean of 19.05. The
 253 mean number of alleles per locus within accessions was 6.51, ranging from 4.23 (Pi_1) to
 254 8.86 (B8H_2) (Table 2). The index H_o varied between 0.52 (CaG_1) and 0.65 (Pi_2), H_e
 255 between 0.63 (Pi_1) and 0.80 (B8H_2), and R_s between 3.77 (Pi_1) and 5.36 (B8H_2)
 256 (Table 2). A total of 35 private alleles were found distributed in 73.3% of the accessions
 257 (Table 2), with only four of them showing frequencies higher than 0.1. In regard to H_e , A
 258 and R_s , the most variable accession was B8H_2, while AM_1, Pe_2, DB_1 and Pi_2
 259 exhibited the highest number of private alleles (Table 2). All accessions showed deviations
 260 from panmixia, with an excess of homozygotes (Table 2).

261

Table 2. Genetic variability in maize landraces from Northwestern Argentina (22 SSR loci)

Accession	N	A		H_o		H_e		R_s		PA	F_{IS}
		M	s.d.	M	s.d.	M	s.d.	M	s.d.		
AM_1	14	5.59	3.54	0.57	0.32	0.66	0.24	3.99	1.74	4	0.14**
AM_2	13	5.91	3.28	0.64	0.22	0.70	0.17	4.22	1.46	1	0.09*
C_1	8	5.27	2.62	0.59	0.20	0.72	0.17	4.39	1.79	0	0.18**
C_2	14	6.77	2.89	0.60	0.23	0.75	0.12	4.56	1.32	0	0.19**
P_1	13	8.14	3.54	0.64	0.18	0.79	0.12	5.29	1.55	2	0.20**
P_2	11	5.41	3.29	0.63	0.28	0.71	0.21	4.23	1.78	0	0.11**
Pe_1	7	4.82	2.24	0.52	0.27	0.67	0.22	4.22	1.73	0	0.23*
Pe_2	15	6.32	3.67	0.55	0.23	0.67	0.24	4.21	1.77	3	0.17**
DB_1	12	7.41	2.79	0.58	0.18	0.79	0.17	5.21	1.43	3	0.27**
DB_2	14	7.27	3.28	0.62	0.18	0.77	0.12	4.90	1.54	1	0.20**
A8H_1	14	7.45	3.25	0.63	0.19	0.76	0.15	4.90	1.50	1	0.18**
A8H_2	15	7.55	4.42	0.62	0.22	0.72	0.23	4.77	1.96	1	0.13**
CaB_2	15	6.36	3.22	0.60	0.24	0.67	0.24	4.26	1.64	1	0.10**
DA_1	15	7.36	3.06	0.61	0.24	0.77	0.13	4.92	1.39	2	0.21**
DA_2	15	7.86	4.60	0.59	0.23	0.70	0.21	4.66	1.91	1	0.16**
CaV_1	12	6.50	3.69	0.55	0.25	0.69	0.25	4.54	1.91	0	0.21**

CaV_2	14	6.77	3.58	0.59	0.23	0.70	0.24	4.60	1.86	2	0.15**
CrA_1	7	5.52	2.02	0.54	0.19	0.79	0.15	4.88	1.50	1	0.31**
CrA_2	15	7.23	4.39	0.63	0.23	0.69	0.24	4.53	1.88	1	0.09**
B8H_1	14	7.00	3.19	0.61	0.20	0.75	0.13	4.69	1.42	0	0.18**
B8H_2	17	8.86	3.67	0.62	0.18	0.80	0.14	5.36	1.47	1	0.23**
M_2	13	5.86	3.08	0.58	0.26	0.66	0.25	4.11	1.70	0	0.10**
CaG_1	8	5.59	2.97	0.52	0.25	0.70	0.28	4.64	2.01	1	0.27**
CaG_2	16	6.86	3.51	0.58	0.26	0.67	0.25	4.32	1.72	1	0.13**
Pi_1	7	4.23	2.49	0.53	0.30	0.63	0.24	3.77	1.97	0	0.12*
Pi_2	14	6.36	3.57	0.65	0.23	0.72	0.20	4.45	1.61	3	0.10**
Cuz_1	11	5.95	3.53	0.53	0.27	0.65	0.27	4.33	2.06	1	0.18**
Cu_1	10	5.82	3.23	0.58	0.19	0.69	0.23	4.41	1.87	2	0.16**
Cu_2	15	6.86	3.60	0.62	0.23	0.70	0.20	4.44	1.64	1	0.11**
Ch_1	11	6.38	3.35	0.57	0.27	0.71	0.22	4.55	1.76	1	0.19**

N: number of individuals. A: number of alleles, Ho: observed heterozygosity, He: expected heterozygosity, Rs: mean allelic richness. PA: private alleles. M: mean, s.d.: standard deviation. The highest value of each index is highlighted in bold. * p<0.05; ** p<0.001.

262

263 Population structure

264 STRUCTURE-model-based approach allowed discrimination of different genetic clusters
 265 within the group of accessions examined here (Fig 3). Using the method of Evanno et al.
 266 (2005), maximal ΔK occurred at K= 2, with the next largest peak at K= 3 (S8 Table).

267

268 **Fig 3. Population structure of maize accessions from Northwestern Argentina (NWA).**
 269 **(a) STRUCTURE bar plot for K=2. (b) STRUCTURE bar plot for K=3.** Each vertical
 270 line represents an individual and colors represent their inferred ancestry from K ancestral
 271 populations. Numbers indicate altitude of collection site for each accession (masl).

272

273 For K=2, most accessions could be assigned to one of the two groups, with an average
 274 proportion of membership higher than 0.85, except for A8H_1 and B8H_2, which showed
 275 an admixed composition (Fig 3a), consistent with the high variability indices observed for
 276 these accessions. The genetic groups did not match with those obtained with the
 277 morphological analysis. The first cluster, yellow, included 10 of the 24 accessions assigned
 278 to group G1, while the second cluster, dark purple, included all the accessions of the
 279 morphological group G2 and 12 of the group G1 (Fig 3a). When considering K=3, the
 280 accessions belonging to the yellow cluster of K=2 still formed a unit, while those of the

281 dark purple cluster became separated into two clusters, blue and pink, one of which
282 coincided with the morphological group G2 (Fig 3b).

283 A detailed examination of Figure 3a revealed that the genetic groups were associated with
284 the altitude of the collection site, with a clear distinction between accessions cultivated
285 below and above 2000 masl (Fig 3a). Figure 4a shows the proportions of membership to the
286 dark purple cluster (K=2) in function of the altitude of the collection site. Although the
287 correlation was significant ($r_{\text{Spearman}} = 0.7$, $p < 0.001$), the pattern was not gradual, exhibiting
288 an abrupt jump above 2000 masl. When these data were overlapped with the assignments
289 found for K=3, the accessions belonging to the yellow group corresponded to the lowest
290 part of the altitude gradient, while those of the pink and blue clusters were cultivated above
291 2000 masl. Indeed, for K=3, the mean altitude of the collection site of the accessions within
292 the yellow, pink and blue clusters were 1684, 2584 and 2745 masl, respectively (Fig 4b).

293

294 **Fig 4. Relationship between population structure and altitude of the collection site.** (a)
295 Scatterplot of altitude vs. the inferred ancestry to STRUCTURE cluster 2 (K=2). (b) Box
296 plots of altitude of collection site for the groups inferred with K=3. Accessions are colour-
297 coded according to STRUCTURE assignment for K=3. Accessions in grey could not be
298 assigned to any of the clusters (admixed).

299

300 The neighbor-joining network based on Nei's distances was consistent with the partition
301 into two groups inferred by STRUCTURE (S2 Fig). In most cases, at the level of individual
302 accessions, no clustering was observed between accessions of a same landrace. The overall
303 difference between accessions was moderate, with $F_{ST}=0.092$ ($p < 0.01$).

304

305 **Isolation by distance and clinal variation**

306 Morphological distances showed no correlation with genetic, geographic or altitudinal
307 distances among accessions. (Fig 5; Mantel test, $p > 0.05$). Conversely, there were
308 significant associations between genetic and altitudinal distances (Fig 5a), as well as
309 between genetic and geographic distances (Fig 5b) (Mantel test, $r=0.44$, $p < 0.001$: $r=0.54$,
310 $p < 0.001$ respectively).

311

312 **Fig 5. Mantel matrix correlation tests. (a) Scatterplot showing the correlation between**
313 **genetic and altitudinal distances. (b) Scatterplot showing the correlation between**
314 **genetic and geographic distances.**

315

316 Despite the absence of correlation between morphological distance and altitude, the
317 characters NL and NKR were negatively associated with the latter (Table 3). Likewise, a
318 decrease in genetic variability was observed with altitude for the indices He and Rs (Figs 6a
319 and 6b, respectively), but not for the estimators A and PA (Spearman correlation, $p>0.05$).

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Table 3. Spearman correlations between agro-morphological traits and altitude.

Trait	Spearman r	p-value
PH	-0.28	0.1394
EH	-0.32	0.0865
NLA	-0.37	0.0443
TI	-0.12	0.5269
NL	-0.61	0.0004
ULL	-0.09	0.62
ULW	-0.02	0.9017
VI	-0.41	0.0229
TL	-0.24	0.2014
TPL	0.39	0.0391

TBS	-0.26	0.1661
NPBT	-0.48	0.0087
NSBT	-0.11	0.5875
NTBT	0.4	0.027
EPL	-0.05	0.8084
MNE	1.20E-03	0.9948
NRK	0.06	0.7592
ED	-0.07	0.7072
NKR	-0.76	<0.0001

Correlations significant after Bonferroni corrections are highlighted in bold ($p < 0.0026$). PH: plant height, NL: number of leaves, NLA: number of leaves above the uppermost ear, ULL: uppermost leaf length, ULW: uppermost leaf width, VI: venation index, TI: tillering index, TL: tassel length, TPL: tassel peduncle length, TBS: tassel branching space, NPBT: number of primary branches on tassel, NSBT: number of secondary branches on tassel, NTBT: number of tertiary branches on tassel, EH: uppermost ear height, EPL: ear peduncle length, ED: ear diameter, MNE: mean number of ears, NRK: number of rows of kernels per ear, NKR: number of kernels per row.

327

328 **Fig 6. Correlation analysis between diversity estimates and altitude of the collection**
329 **site. (a) Scatterplot of the correlation between altitude and expected Heterozygosity,**
330 **He. (b) Scatterplot of the correlation between altitude and allelic richness, Rs.**

331

332

333 Discussion

334

335 Efficient use and conservation of the landraces available in germplasm banks requires
336 comprehensive genetic and agronomic characterization focused primarily on variation at
337 the level of individual accessions [3,36–38]. Consistent with this idea, our results suggest
338 that racial assignment, even when performed according to the standardized criteria of
339 germplasm banks, is a poor indicator of similarity between accessions, at both genetic and
340 morphological levels. The lack of racial cohesion may be explained by the dynamics of
341 production and exchange of landraces among local farmers. Small holders in NWA, just
342 like in Mexico [39,40], and most probably in the rest of Latin America, have adopted

343 cultivation practices that allow unintentional racial crossing, as they grow different maize
344 forms or varieties in small areas close to each other, thus facilitating pollen exchange. At
345 the same time, producers usually exchange grains, promoting gene flow through the
346 dispersal of different maize forms among geographically distant localities. Moreover, the
347 introduction of commercial or improved germplasm, which generally provides economic
348 benefits for farmers, has also contributed to blur racial boundaries. In fact, the mixing of
349 such germplasm with native landraces produces creolized varieties that farmers would later
350 identify as “local”.

351 In this study, the clusters derived from morphological characters are consistent with those
352 previously described for NWA landraces. Melchiorre et al. [41,42] identified two major
353 maize groups: the first one, regarded as more primitive, is related to the popcorn type
354 (Pisingallo) with early maturity, rather corneous grains and smaller plants; the second
355 group is more heterogeneous, with totally or partially corneous or floury grains and larger
356 plants. The landraces studied here display the same pattern, where groups are associated
357 with the type of endosperm and the main discriminating characters are related to plant size
358 (PH, EH, TBS and NLA).

359 The two major groups identified in the molecular analysis did not coincide with the
360 morphological groups and showed a clear association with the altitude of collection sites,
361 with the morphological group G2 being completely included in the highland group (>2000
362 masl). The levels of variability also appeared to go along with the differentiation of genetic
363 groups, with a decrease in parameters such as expected heterozygosity and allelic richness
364 in function of altitude. The lower variability of the highland group is consistent with the
365 difficulties in growing maize under harsh environmental conditions. In the highlands,
366 frequent frosts and low temperatures shorten flowering and maturation times, thus reducing
367 seed yields. Consequently, population sizes tend to be smaller, intensifying the effect of
368 genetic drift and promoting the loss of diversity.

369 Regardless of how variability is distributed, NWA landraces taken as a whole show high
370 levels of diversity, which are similar to the values recorded at the centers of crop origin.
371 The SSR loci analyzed here are a subset of those evaluated by Vigouroux et al. [5]. When
372 limiting the comparisons to this subset of loci, the mean number of alleles detected in the
373 present study ($A=19.05$) is slightly lower than that reported by Vigouroux et al. (2008) for

374 both the Highland Mexico (A=20.4) and Andean (A=21.45) groups. Likewise, the
375 estimates of H_e varied within a range previously reported for landraces from all over the
376 Americas (0.61-0.81) [5,9,10,39,43,44]. These results emphasize the potential value of the
377 NWA landraces conserved in the BAP, since only 30 accessions contained almost the same
378 number of alleles as germplasm coming from the central regions of maize distribution.
379 Several studies have found a relationship between altitude of collection site and genetic
380 composition of maize landraces both at the regional and continental levels [8,10,45]. The
381 existence of correlation between genetic differentiation and altitude may be interpreted as
382 resulting from clinal variation, where the genetic distances increase gradually with
383 increasing altitudinal distance. However, in the landraces analyzed here, the relationship
384 between altitude and inferred ancestry to the clusters obtained by STRUCTURE (Fig 4a)
385 suggests a more abrupt cutoff, where the accessions of intermediate position are those
386 showing a signature of recent introgression.
387 On the other hand, although morphological differentiation was not found to be correlated
388 with altitude, individual trait analysis revealed a significant decrease for NL and NRK.
389 Considering that all measurements were made in a common garden experiment at 2300
390 masl, these results may be interpreted as a local adaptation rather than phenotypic plasticity
391 in response to environmental conditions. In fact, the relationship between flowering time,
392 which is a key factor in the adaptation of landraces to altitude [46,47], and NL has been
393 extensively documented [48–52]. In particular, Li et al [53] showed that flowering time
394 shared genetic determinants with the number of leaves below, but not above, the uppermost
395 ear (NLA). These results may help explain why we found an association between NL, but
396 not NLA, and altitude.
397 As observed here for NL, the reduction in genome size with altitude has been proposed to
398 be an indirect consequence of selection on flowering time [54]. In agreement with these
399 hypotheses, NWA landraces also exhibit patterns of clinal variation for both the DNA
400 content of autosomes and the occurrence of B chromosomes [17,55]. Evidence of their
401 adaptive significance was provided by Lia et al. (2007).
402 Alternative scenarios can be postulated to explain the genetic structuring pattern found in
403 this study, i.e., the existence of two well-differentiated groups, one below and the other
404 above 2000 masl, in a relatively small area. Rivas [56] compared the genetic relationships

405 between the materials analyzed here and those included in the studies of Vigouroux et al.
406 [5], Lia et al. [16] and Bracco et al. [57]. This author found that the landraces at the lower
407 part of the altitudinal gradient were assigned to the Tropical Lowland cluster [5], while
408 those from the highland zone were assigned to the Andean cluster. These two groups have
409 been related to distinct events of maize dispersal in South America [58,59], suggesting the
410 current coexistence of two genetic pools of different age in NWA, namely, landraces that
411 entered through the eastern lowlands of the continent and those introduced from the Central
412 Andes. Indeed, Vigouroux et al. [5] had already considered the idea of a secondary contact
413 zone encompassing Bolivia, Argentina, Paraguay and Uruguay, where typical Andean
414 landraces became mixed with those from the eastern lowlands of South America. More
415 recently, Kistler et al. [60] proposed the existence of three major maize lineages in South
416 America. Two of these, the Andean and Lowland lineages, derived from a partially
417 domesticated maize that had been introduced to south-western Amazon at early stages. The
418 third lineage, Pan-American, was introduced later through lowland South America. In this
419 scenario, available information is still insufficient to establish putative relationships
420 between the lowland lineages postulated by Kistler et al. [60] and the lowland NWA
421 landraces. In addition to the uncertainties concerning the movements of maize during pre-
422 Columbian times, the influence of the varieties and hybrids resulting from modern breeding
423 is another factor to be considered when interpreting the genetic composition of maize from
424 NWA. In this regard, Cámara Hernández et al. [13] provided numerous examples of
425 creolized landraces, particularly for the lowlands. Likewise, evidence obtained with
426 chloroplast genome sequencing support the occurrence of introgression between traditional
427 landraces and more modernly improved varieties [61].

428 In conclusion, the present study constitutes a valuable contribution to existing *ex situ*
429 conservation programs and to design future collection and management strategies. In
430 particular, our results indicate that altitudinal structuring is a key factor in decision-making.
431 For example, Perales et al. [62] reported that the replacement rate of native landraces by
432 modern varieties in Mexico was considerably higher in lowlands and mid-elevation sites
433 than in highlands because there were few modern varieties capable of outperforming native
434 materials in high-altitude environments. These findings led them to suggest that
435 interventions should favor *in situ* conservation strategies in lowland or intermediate

436 elevation sites, where modern varieties have largely outcompeted native landraces. Despite
437 the lack of similar studies in NWA landraces, it is clear that the altitudinal structuring of
438 genetic diversity constitutes a relevant factor to be considered for their conservation.

439

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441

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445

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637

638 **Supporting information**

- 639
- 640 S1 Fig. This is the S1 Fig Title. This is the S1 Fig legend.
- 641 S2 Fig. This is the S2 Fig Title. This is the S2 Fig legend.
- 642 S1 Table. This is the S1 Table Title. This is the S1 Table legend.
- 643 Fig_S1_PCA_individuos_PC3_PC1
- 644 Fig_S2_NJ_ssr_379.tree
- 645
- 646 1_Supplementary Table_S1_Accessions
- 647 2_Supplementary Table_S2_primers
- 648 3_Supplementary Table_S3_Morphologicaldata
- 649 4_Supplementary Table_S4_Correlations
- 650 5_Supplementary Table_S5_PCA_contributions
- 651 6_Supplementary Table_S6_SSR_data
- 652 7_Supplementary Table_S7_Genetic_diversity
- 653 8_Supplementary Table_S8_Evanno_deltaK
- 654

Fig1

Fig2

Fig3

Fig4

a)

b)

Fig5

Fig6